

"DENOTATIC GRAPH" IN THE STUDY OF GRAMMAR TOPICS IN RUSSIAN LESSONS

¹Chorieva Sharofat Turaevna, ²Avazov Fuzail Ahmed ogli

¹Lecturer, Department of Russian Language and Literature, Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

²Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8226277>

Abstract. *This article proposes the effective implementation of the "Denotative Graph" graphic organizer in the process of studying grammatical topics in Russian language lessons, the main purpose of which is to form students' conscious mastery of complex concepts of Russian grammar. Organizer "Denotative graph" helps to simplify the study of a grammatical topic.*

Keywords: *graphic organizers, teaching aids, functions of didactic tools, denotation graph.*

Graphic organizers help develop the ability to work with information: they make it possible to highlight the main thing, translate information into a specific organizer, scheme, algorithm, table, with the help of which a concise idea is presented in a schematic and verbal form.

Graphic organizers – structuring information in a logical order on a sheet of paper, blackboard (or screen of technical means) that are used to improve memorization, assimilation, analysis or application of what has been learned. These tools help the student to schematically present complex information in a simple way.

We will focus on the following functions of didactic tools, including graphic organizers:

- illustrative
- communicative
- cognitive function.

Illustrative function – it is the transmission of information in a visual form, which helps to develop logical thinking.

Cognitive functions of a person is the ability of an individual to perceive information from the outside, process it, understand, study, realize and process (remember, transmit, use) the relationships and relationships between them. This is the highest nervous activity in which the personality manifests itself. This function of the brain, a set of processes by which a person cognizes the world, himself and interacts with the surrounding reality.

Communicative function implies understanding of speech, the ability of participants in a speech act for fruitful and useful communication. Knowledge and observance of the rules of the modern literary language enables effective communication. Language is, first of all, a means of communication, a means of human communication.

Practically working on graphic organizers, you can implement all of the above functions. Students can complete the graphical learning tools individually, in pairs, groups, or together with the teacher. They can be used both for consolidation and for explaining new material. In the classroom, well-known graphic organizers are often used, such as a cluster, Euler circles, Venn diagrams, mental maps, a Fishbone diagram, etc.

A denotative graph (from the Latin denoto - "I designate" and the Greek "I write") is a way of isolating the essential features of a key concept from the text. [2, p. 71]

The main topic is written at the top of the organizer. In the next row, verbs that reveal the essence of the issue, even lower - the specification of the concept for each verb. Consider the technology of compiling this organizer in more detail.

1. Definition of the main topic (words or phrases).
2. Selection of main verbs that reveal the essence of the main concept that links the key concept and its essential feature (verbs denoting the goal: direct, suggest, lead, give, etc.; verbs denoting the process of achieving the result: achieve, implement; verbs denoting the prerequisites for achieving the result: to be based, based, based; linking verbs, with the help of which the definition of the meaning of the concept is reached).
3. define an expression or a word that correlates each branch with a keyword in order to eliminate any inconsistencies, contradictions.

For example, a denotative graph was compiled on the topic "Adverb".

In this case, the organizer is used to comprehend the grammatical topic, provides unification, systematization of information. Develops systemic thinking, the ability to structure, systematize information. Understanding grammatical topics is not always possible. Pupils answer questions, but comprehend, of course, not easy. And the teacher should simplify the concepts, present it in a simpler form, so that it can be seen and understood, as if on the shelves. The

denotation graph technique serves to teach the student to comprehend information; in fact, he himself is a tool of comprehension, which in a certain way describes the concept, revealing its aspects. Branches-verbs depart from the concept-trunk, and branches-names depart from them. Verbs are the basic actions and relations inherent in a concept; names are those concepts and phenomena with which the main concept is associated. Let's try to consider this organizer on the topic "Complex sentences with subordinate conditions" of grade 9 with Uzbek and other languages of instruction.

The topics are complex even for Russians, but when the organizer is introduced in all types of complex sentences in the same form, it gives noticeable results. The systematization of concepts, the allocation of verbs in a row, and nouns in the next row draws a certain picture in which you can even tell a part, but with your own verb.

The graphic organizer was tested in schools in the Surkhandarya region, Namangan and Tashkent regions. In the introduction of the organizer in the classroom in grades 9-10 (with the Uzbek language of instruction) was attended by teachers from the 3rd school of the Kumkurgan district of the Surkhandarya region Hudaykulov A.A., from the 58th school of the Davlatabad district of the Namangan region - Sayyora Olimzhanovna, Ismailova N., Tursunbayeva G.T., Dzhurabaeva N.A., Sotivoldieva R.O. and from the 49th school - Rakhimova Yu.T., Kirgizboeva I.T., Rustamzhonova Sh.A, Rakhmonova M.D., from the 17th school of the Bustanlyk district of the Tashkent region Idirova S.Yu., from the 19th school of the same district Salimova G.V., Karabaeva A.Kh.

Drawing conclusions from the experiments, it should be emphasized that in these classes the use of the graphic organizer "Denotative graph" increased communication skills by 35-40%, increased the efficiency of mastering information, contributed to the development of communicative competence and allowed:

1. Qualitatively and consciously master grammatical topics by students;
2. Structure the information in accordance with the focus of the educational material;
3. To increase the effectiveness of learning in the study of parts of speech and types of complex sentences;
4. Make information as perceptible and accessible as possible.

The introduction of new pedagogical technologies, graphic organizers in the educational process is the call of the times. The teacher must constantly work on himself, be creative, create various forms and methods of new pedagogical technologies, skillfully use them in the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. Авазова, С. А. (2021). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ГРАФИЧЕСКОГО ОРГАНАЙЗЕРА «ТОПОР» («ТОПОР, СРУБИВШИЙ ГЕНИЕВ») НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ РАЗНЫХ ДИСЦИПЛИН. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(NUU Conference 1), 182-186.
2. Лебедева, М.Б. Подходы к педагогическому проектированию курсов дистанционного обучения [Электронный ресурс] / М.Б. Лебедева // Дистанционные образовательные технологии. Материалы: Статьи участников конференции РОИС-2007. – Режим доступа: <http://rois.loiro.ru/index.php?module=articles&action=view&cid=0&id=71>.
3. Тураевна, Ч. Ш. ., Ахмедовна, А. С. ., & Ахмед углов, А. Ф. . (2023). Изучение Биографии М.Ю.Лермонтова И Его Стихотворения «Три Пальмы» При Помощи Графических Органайзеров И Схем. *Място Пиислоски* , 32 , 185–190. Получено с <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1125>.
4. Усманова Р. Русский язык: Учебник для 9 класса школ общего среднего образования с узбекским и другими языками обучения/ Р. Усманова и др. – Ташкент: ИПТД “Узбекистан”, 2019. – 160 стр.
5. Худойкулов Х.Ж. Замонавий педагогик технология таълим самарадорлигининг асосидир. - Т.: «Навруз», 2013.
6. Худойкулов Х., Чориева Ш. Использование схемы «Почему?» при формировании и развитии коммуникативной компетенции учеников на уроках русского языка. *PEDAGOGIK MANORAT*ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ МАСТЕРСТВО*PEDAGOGICAL SKILL* 4, 2021 с.54-57.)
7. Чориева, Ш., Сохибжамол, А., & Ахмедов, . Ф. (2023). ГРАФИЧЕСКИЙ ОРГАНАЙЗЕР «Я И КОМПЬЮТЕР» В ПОМОЩЬ ОБУЧАЮЩЕМУ. *Наука и инновация*, 1(3), 23–26. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/si/article/view/13101>
8. Turaevna, C. S., & Akhmedovna, A. S. (2021). The use of fishban in the study of literature. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(8), 559-564.
9. Цылова Е.Г., Экгауз Е. Я., Парамонов Д.Н. КЛАСТЕРЫ И ДЕНОТАТНЫЕ ГРАФЫ. Х международная научно-методическая конференция «Новые образовательные технологии в вузе», Уральский институт экономики, управления и права г. Каменск-Уральский https://elar.urfu.ru/bitstream/10995/26655/1/notv_2013_196.pdf